

MANAGEMENT EFFICIENCY AND PERFORMANCE OF PACS – A QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS

Dr. Sanjib Kumar Hota

Madhusudan Institute of Cooperative Management, Bhubaneswar-751012, Odisha

Article History

Received on: 21-Mar 2026

Revised on: 28-Apr-2026

Accepted on: 25- May 2026

First Published: 04-Jun-2026

Cite this Article as

SK Hota (2026), “management efficiency and performance of PACS – a quantitative analysis”, *International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management*, Volume 14, Issue1, 2026, pp 195-208

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20542764>

ABSTRACT

The management efficiency is attributed to several factors such as governance, professionalism and operational control mechanisms etc. In cooperative structure the assessment of management efficiency and managerial effectiveness is relatively complex as compared to that of corporate structure. Because, the cooperatives are members' driven and hence often experienced the problems of free rider (responsibility of all is responsibility of none), adverse selection (pre-contractual-hidden information), moral hazard (post-contractual opportunism), median voter and log-rolling etc.. These problems are hindering the management efficiency and managerial effectiveness of cooperatives causing ineffective performance of cooperative institutions. However, cooperatives being owned by the members and governed through democratic mechanism to achieve the common goal are making their legitimate internal strategies in adherence to the exogenous factors like control of the Government through Registrar of Cooperative Societies (RCS) and other financing, refinancing, licensing financial institutions/banks etc. for their sustainable performance.

An attempt has been made in this study to analyse the effect of management efficiency/ managerial effectiveness on the performance of Primary Agricultural Cooperative Society (PACS) based on primary data collected from 300 samples of 50 PACS and also secondary data to analyse the effect of various factors on management efficiency / managerial effectiveness and thereby on performance of PACS. The external control emphasizing the role of RCS is found as one of the significant factors to improve the performance of PACSs in Odisha state.

Key Words: PACS, Managerial Effectiveness, Governance, External Control.

Introduction

“A cooperative is an autonomous association of persons united voluntarily to meet their common economic, social, and cultural needs and aspirations through a jointly owned and democratically-controlled enterprise.” (International Cooperative Alliance, 1995)

Primary Agricultural Cooperative Society (PACS) is also a jointly owned and democratically controlled enterprise to meet the common economic, social, and cultural needs of its

members. The membership is open to all who are voluntarily interested and eligible to be a member of PACS. The main objective of PACS is to undertake the Short-term agricultural credit business along with other businesses as per the provisions of Bye-law for the economic development of its members. However, the sphere and scope of undertaking multiple business activities by PACS has expanded with the amendment made in the bye-law of PACS in line with the provisions of Model Bye-law came into force in the year 2023 in all most all the states of India being one of the major initiatives of Ministry of Cooperation, Govt. of India.

The Cooperative movement in India is having a vast network covering around 100% of the household as its members of cooperatives. There are nearly 1 lakh PACS with 13 crore of members in India. The credit cooperatives in agricultural sector has its significant importance in catering mainly the agricultural credit needs of rural farming community. There are three tier structures of Short-Term Credit Cooperative Structure (STCCS) such as PACS at grass-root level, DCCB (District Central Bank at district/regional level, StCB (State Cooperative Bank) at the apex level in the state) in the state under study i.e. Odisha State.

The credential and brand image of PACS in some of the states in India is praiseworthy whereas in some other state their performance is below the desired level.. Despite the disparities in the functioning of the PACSs in different parts of the country, the role of PACSs in dispensing credit for rural sector can be considered as one of the parameters of inclusive development. Thus the Governance, Professional management, External control, Management Efficiency/Managerial effectiveness and performance of the PACSs are to be analysed for deducing certain significant conclusions for policy prescription for the growth and survival of PACSs.

Objectives

An attempt has been made in this study to analyse the relationship between and among the parameters like Governance, Professional Management, External Control, Management efficiency / Managerial Effectiveness and Performance so as to deduce certain conclusion which may be useful for policy prescription.

The pattern of relationship the study aims to analyse is depicted in **Figure-1** so as to infer certain conclusive remark on the factor (s) affecting the performance of PACSs.

The hypotheses pertaining to this objective have been formulated and tested (based on SME results shown in Table-1 and the relationship supported by diagrammatic presentation of SEM as shown in Figure-2).

Hypotheses and Results

1. Governance would positively influence Management efficiency /Managerial Effectiveness.
It is not significant as P value 0.505 is found more than 0.05, CR value -0.667 is found less than 1.96. So it is not supporting the hypothesis. Further, it is negatively related as standardised regression coefficient is -0.032.
2. Professional Management would positively influence Management Efficiency/ Managerial Effectiveness.
It is not significant as P value 0.192 is found more than 0.05, CR value 1.306 is found less than 1.96. So it is not supporting the hypothesis. However, it is positively related as standardised regression coefficient is 0.041.
3. External Control would positively influence Managerial Effectiveness.
It is significant as P value 0.000 is found, less than 0.05, CR value 4.105 is found more than 1.96. So it is supporting the hypothesis. Further, it is positively related as standardised regression coefficient is 1.033. Refer:
4. Management Efficiency / Effectiveness would positively influence Performance.
It is significant as P value 0.000 is found, less than 0.05, CR value 4.109 is found more than 1.96. So it is supporting the hypothesis. Further, it is positively related as standardised regression coefficient is 1.020.

Data Base and Methodology

The study is based on primary sources of data collected based on a pre-designed questionnaire from 300 samples selected at random from various stakeholders (Employees, Board of Directors and Members) from 50 Nos. of randomly selected PACSs in Odisha. The secondary sources of data from the annual reports and financial statements of the PACS under study has also been gathered on specific parameters for undertaking certain analysis pertaining to the performance of PACSs.

The perceptions of the respondents on certain selected parameters in 5 point likert scales such as 5. Strongly Agree, 4. Agree, 3. Neutral, 2. Disagree and 1. Strongly Disagree. The responses are analysed based on the frequency distribution of responses of respondents on various parameters. Further, in order to analyse the relationship between/among different parameters affecting the performance of the PACSs the STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODEL (SEM) estimated by using software AMOS OF SPSS- VERSION- 22 has been applied. Based on the Factor Analysis the parameters considered under different heads of analysis has been reduced and the resultant parameters are considered for SEM. The perceptions of the respondents on various parameters assessed through 5 point likert scale have been considered for SEM (after reducing the variable on the basis of Factor Loading).

Result and discussion

The parameters or variables considered for analysis under different heads such as Governance Professional Management, External Control, Management efficiency (i.e. Managerial Effectiveness) and Performance are given below.

Governance (Gov)

Sl.No	Parameters
1	The PACS prepares and discloses audited annual financial statements in accordance with the Generally Accepted Accounting Principles
2	The PACS discloses capital adequacy position on a regular basis
3	The PACS discloses information related to the classification of assets and provisioning norms
4	The PACS discloses information on its profit, risk and assets etc
5	The PACS discloses information about its business network and services provided
6	The PACS discloses information related to customer service, such as grievance redressal mechanisms and customer complaints.
7	Boards of Directors (BODs) and CEO of PACS always ensure proper audit on time
8	PACS makes sincerely the bank reconciliation statements.
9	PACS undertakes proper loan appraisal system so as to minimise the risk of recovery of loan
10	The president and BODs insist always to minimise operational/ liquidity/ credit risk etc. and ensure that the risk policy of the PACS is properly implemented
11	Board of management includes directors with special knowledge and practical experience.
12	Attendance and participation of Board of Directors during audit of PACS
13	The PACS maintains rigorous practices, ensuring that their decision-making processes are open to scrutiny relating to loan processing and sanctioning etc.

Professional Management (PM)

Sl. No.	Parameters
1	The CEO prepares / certifies prudently all reports and schedules, which is to be placed in the Board and in the AGM (Annual General Body Meeting).
2	Inspection and quality of audit with more professionalism is being made within the current structure.
3	Appointment of internal auditors is being made objectively.
4	Accountability policy approved by the BOD exists for detecting serious lapses, irregularities/frauds by the official and board of directors.
5	Accountability policy approved by the BOD exists for detecting serious lapses, irregularities/frauds by the staff.
6	Information and cyber-security policy approved by the BOD exists.

7	Compliance department/officer exists and reports directly to the board/CEO.
8	.Reports and written are regularly submitted to the authority concerned
9	Board is approving HR Policy consisting of qualifications, selection, training, remuneration etc. exists in the PACS.
10	PACS is having CEO with board approved qualifications.
11	Regular training is provided to BoDs (Board of Directors)
12	Regular training provided to Employees
	Continuous Improvement
13	The PACS fosters a culture of continuous improvement by encouraging innovation, adopting best practices in consonance with emerging trends and technologies.
14	The PACS adopts regularly review processes and policies to identify areas for enhancement.

External Control (EC)

Sl. No.	Parameters
1	RBI and NABARD have been trying in ensuring corporate governance in the PACSs
2	The RCS and the cooperative department officers are professionally qualified / trained to control and monitor PACS.
3	The role of RCS to ensure proper control of PACs through administrative, elections, auditing related matters
4	The DDCBs/StCB has full control over PACS being the financing Banks for PACS
5	Recent reforms cooperative sector and amendment in Bye-law will be of helpful to the effective management of PACS
6	NABARD does not enjoy the powers to regulate PACS in matters relating to governance and resolution.
7	The duality of control/regulation is one of the main hindrances for the more effective management of PACS
	RCS Control
8	The AGCS (Auditor General of Cooperative Societies) and officials AGCS are to ensure transparency and accountability in PACS through Audit
9	The role NABARD to ensures proper control of PACS being refinancing Bank for STCCS (Short Term Credit Cooperative Structure)
10	Auditors appointed from the panel of RCS/AGCS are professionally competent and rigorously trained

Managerial Effectiveness (ME)

Sl. No.	Parameters
1	The PACS effectively manages its costs, as indicated by the proportion of total expenses relative to total income.

2	The PACSs are mobilising their deposits effectively for high-earning advances.
3	The management of the PACS is proficient in generating income from non-credit businesses, showcasing their ability to diversify income streams
4	The PACS operates efficiently with a smaller workforce, reflecting the effectiveness of its operational management.
5	The PACSs are demonstrating efficiency in risk management and capital adequacy.

Performance (PR)

Sl. No.	Parameters
1	External control and oversight contribute to thereby positively impacting the Net profit.
2	External control and oversight contribute to thereby positively impacting the loans and advances
3	Effective governance and Professional management practices significantly enhances the financial performance (Net profit).
4	Effective governance and Professional management practices significantly enhances the financial performance (Loans and Advances).

The elements from the different broad parameters considered for the study were analysed through Factor analysis (Factor Extraction Method-Principal Component Analysis) and based on the higher value of Factor Loading (as depicted in Table-2) the elements are selected for undertaking the SEM. The factors extracted are as follows

Factors extracted from Factor Analysis

Sl. No.	
	Governance (Gov.)
4	The PACS discloses information on its profit, risk and assets etc
11	Board of management includes directors with special knowledge and practical experience.
	Professional Management (PM)
4	Accountability policy approved by the BOD exists for detecting serious lapses, irregularities/frauds by the official and board of directors.
9	Board is approving HR Policy consisting of qualifications, selection, training, remuneration etc. exists in the PACS
13	The PACS fosters a culture of continuous improvement by encouraging innovation, adopting best practices in consonance with emerging trends and technologies.
	External Control (EC)

2	The RCS and the cooperative department officers are professionally qualified / trained to control and monitor PACS.
3	The role of RCS to ensure proper control of PACs through administrative, elections, auditing related matters
	Managerial Effectiveness (ME)
1	The PACS effectively manages its costs, as indicated by the proportion of total expenses relative to total income.
2	The PACSs are mobilising their deposits effectively for high-earning advances.
	Performance (PR)
1	External control and oversight contribute to thereby positively impacting the Net profit.
2	External control and oversight contribute to thereby positively impacting the loans and advances

STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODELING (SEM)

SEM is a diverse set of methods used by scientists doing both observational and experimental research. SEM is used mostly in the social and behavioural sciences, business research and other fields. A definition of SEM is difficult without reference to technical language. It is a statistical technique combining regression and confirmatory factor analysis. SEM involves a model representing how various aspects of some phenomenon are thought to causally connect to one another. The postulated structuring in SEM can also be presented using diagrams containing arrows. The causal structures imply that specific patterns should appear among the values of the observed variables. This makes it possible to use the connections between the observed variables' values to estimate the magnitudes of the postulated effects, and to test whether or not the observed data are consistent with the requirements of the hypothesized causal structures.

In this study SEM is applied by using the available set of data on the selected parameters and the connection between / among the parameters observed based on the diagram (Fig.2) and related statistics estimated by the model. The model also provide insight whether to support or not the hypotheses formulated. The detailed SME analysis made are as follows.

Figure-2 Diagramic representation of SEM

Table 1: Structural Model Results (Hypothesis Testing)

Structural Path Estimates

Hypothesis	Structural Path	Estimate (β)	S.E.	C.R.	P-value	Result
H1	Governance → Managerial Effectiveness	-0.015	0.022	-0.667	0.505	Not Supported
H2	Professional Management → Managerial Effectiveness	0.036	0.028	1.306	0.192	Not Supported
H3	External Control → Managerial Effectiveness	0.362	0.088	4.105	<0.001	Supported
H4	Managerial Effectiveness → Performance	2.298	0.559	4.109	<0.001	Supported

Table- 1(a)

Standardized Regression Coefficients

Path	Standardized β
Governance → Managerial Effectiveness	-0.032
Professional Management → Managerial Effectiveness	0.041
External Control → Managerial Effectiveness	1.033
Managerial Effectiveness → Performance	1.020

The following observations can be drawn from the analysis of Table 1 and 1(a).

- Governance has a negative but insignificant effect on Managerial Effectiveness.
- Professional Management positively influences Managerial Effectiveness but not significantly.
- External Control significantly improves Managerial Effectiveness.
- Managerial Effectiveness significantly enhances Performance.

Table 2: Measurement Model and Model Fit Indices

Model Fit Summary

Fit Index	Recommended Value	Obtained Value	Interpretation
χ^2 (CMIN)	Lower value preferred	277.509	Acceptable
df	-	56	-
χ^2/df (CMIN/DF)	< 5.0	4.955	Good Fit
GFI	≥ 0.80	0.839	Good Fit
AGFI	≥ 0.70	0.713	Acceptable Fit
CFI	≥ 0.90	0.936	Excellent Fit
TLI	≥ 0.90	0.956	Excellent Fit
RMSEA	≤ 0.08	0.080	Acceptable Fit
NFI	≥ 0.90	0.918	Good Fit
IFI	≥ 0.90	0.938	Good Fit

Convergent Validity and Factor Loadings

Construct	Indicator	Standardized Loading
Governance	Gov11	0.730
Governance	Gov4	0.207
Professional Management	PM9	0.433
Professional Management	PM4	0.434
Professional Management	PM13	0.772

External Control	EC3	0.959
External Control	EC2	0.451
Managerial Effectiveness	ME2	0.238
Managerial Effectiveness	ME1	0.250
Performance	PR1	0.739
Performance	PR2	0.946

The following observation found from the analysis of Table (2).

The model demonstrates satisfactory goodness-of-fit. Most fit indices exceed recommended threshold values, indicating that the proposed theoretical framework adequately represents the observed data.

It is observed from the above table that in the regression weight, it is found that some parameter estimates are high significant and some are not. In other words, two of them are significantly differently from 0. The interpretations on the parameter estimates are straight forward except Managerial Effectiveness (ME) with Governance (GOV). For example, ME can decrease by 0.015 units for each 1-unit increase in GOV. Similarly, ME increases by 0.036 for each 1.00-unit increase in Professional Management (PM). Moreover, ME increases by 0.362 unit for each 1.00-unit increase in External Control (EC) which is also found significant.

Similarly, Performance (PR) can increase by 2.298 unit with each 1.00-unit increase in ME which is also highly significant. The correlation structure between the errors is also estimated by AMOS with significant results.

It can be deduced from the analysis that the governance is contributing negatively to the managerial effectiveness which may be attributed to asymmetry of information, ineffective risk management strategy and lapses or irregularities in internal control and apathetic attitude or inactive participation of board of directors. The cooperatives in general and PACSs in particular are normally suffering from inactive (passive) participation of members in General body meeting or in business or in development of the PACS which is mainly due to lack of proper information flow (inflow and out flow). The risk management strategies and internal control system is observed often is not so sound in PACS as compared to corporate sector / nationalised bank which may be attributed to lack of knowledge, skill and attitude along with politicisation and bureaucratisation of several performances linked governance parameters. Further, even though the Board of Directors are the real policy makers in cooperatives of any types including PACSs, many of them lacks knowledge in many crucial aspects of the PACS and to certain extent politicised certain issues which affects the accountability, transparency and credibility of PACS. Thus good governance in PACSs can bring managerial effectiveness and the UCBs under study should revisit the governance process to improve the managerial effectiveness.

The professional Management has a positive impact on the managerial effectiveness as because the professional management of the activities not only helps in rendering effective services but also adds to the membership or customer base of the organisation which may be reflected in their brand image and ultimately in the performance of the PACSs or cooperatives. However, in many of the cooperatives from Primary to apex professionalism is lacking in terms of skilled manpower and pace of digitisation as compared to their competitors. As a result of which the accounting, auditing, supervising, compliance, reporting and adherence to the norms regulatory framework often got either delayed or improper. However, with the help of capacity building or Training programme for employees and Board of Directors and through appropriate HR Policy many of the PACSs might have been trying for improving the pace of professionalism and thereby managerial effectiveness. So it is found having positive relation with managerial effectiveness but not significant. Thus, required and appropriate steps should be taken by the PACSs to improve the standard and status of professional management so as to sustain in the competitive environment.

The external Control (control of RCS) has a positive and significant impact on managerial effectiveness. The managerial effectiveness has a broader sense to understand and hence it is influenced by many variables such as governance, professionalism, external control etc. which is reflected in terms of increase in income of the organisation in a cost effective manner as result of which the performance will ultimately be positively influenced. In cooperatives in general it is often observed that the democratic control and members' participation criteria / principles often misinterpreted for personal benefit or for cheap popularity or for ego satisfaction or for political / bureaucratic affiliation etc. as a result of which sometimes the operations and management got disturbed and hence tends towards mismanagement. However, it is the controller/ supervisor/ regulatory has a vigil on the functioning of the PACSs and hence it makes them compelled often to go back to the right track if deviated little in any from the regulatory frame work which in turn helps them to regain their managerial effectiveness if lost to certain extent as because their survival will be at stake if they cannot satisfy the regulatory framework under which they are functioning. The influence of RCS in the case of PACS is realised relatively more than that of DDCB/StCB in certain cases of importance (maintaining key indicators /parameters of banking) even though both have their respective legitimate role to perform. Thus, it can be inferred that had there been no external control mechanism, the internal factors or forces in isolation in PACSs may not be in a position to restore or improve (whichever the case may be) the managerial effectiveness which will ultimately be reflected in their performance. Thus the external control and managerial effectiveness are positive and significantly related.

The managerial effectiveness has a positive and significant impact on the Performance of PACs. The managerial effectiveness broadly reflected in terms of income, expenditure, cost of management, borrowing capacity, volume of business (advances and deposits), performance of employees and pace of business diversification etc. besides other motivational and skill development issues. Thus, if managerial effectiveness is ensured in a desired manner within the regulatory framework then definitely the performance of the PACSs will be enhanced. Thus the parameters of managerial effectiveness should be handled

with utmost care by PACSs to improve their performance as managerial effectiveness has a direct impact on performance. In many of the PACSs this relationship is found positive and significant and in some other it seems to be positive. However, managerial effectiveness in PACSs in India is found to have positive impact on performance and hence it should be taken care by all PACSs.

The results shown in above table provide a summarised overview of the model fit, which includes the value (277.509) along with its degrees of freedom (56) and probability value (0.000). In the table NPAR stands for Number of parameters and CMIN (Chi-Square) is the minimum discrepancy and represents the discrepancy between the unrestricted sample covariance matrix and the restricted covariance matrix. DF stands for degrees of freedom and P is the probability value.

In SEM a relatively small chi-square value supports the proposed theoretical model being tested. In this model the value is 277.509 and is small compared to the value of the independence model (1522.154). Hence the value is good, signifying acceptable model fit.

The model fit indices also provide a reasonable model fit for the structural model. Goodness of Fit index (GFI) obtained is 0.839. The Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI) is 0.713. The Comparative Fit index (CFI), Tucker Lewis Index (TLI) are 0.936 and 0.956 respectively. RMSEA is 0.08. Hence it is concluded that the proposed research model fits the data reasonably.

Findings

1. The Governance has a negative relationship with Managerial effectiveness.
2. The professional management has a positive relationship with Managerial effectiveness even though not significant.
3. The External control has a positive and significant relationship with Managerial effectiveness.
4. The Managerial effectiveness has a positive and significant impact on Performance

Suggestions

1. The structure, pattern and process of governance in PACSs may be reengineered and revamp through appropriate changes in bye-laws or Act if needed. The governance process must be friendly to employees, members, customers and has the adaptability to cope of with the changes in business, regulation and pace of digitization. The pragmatic and situational approach of leadership should be focused upon to ensure the features of good governance in cooperatives.
2. Professionalism through continuous capacity building / training programmes in desired fields should be adopted as mandatory policy by PACSs along with need based and situation base HR Policy coupled with a varieties of financial and non-financial motivational tools. Professional management can only be ensured provide

the skill, knowledge, attitude and adaptability to change of employees and board of directors are taken care of properly by PACSs. So the PACSs should make efforts to ensure professionalism in functioning which will lead them to fruitful performance

3. The Reserve Bank of India (RBI), NABARD and Registrar of Cooperative Societies should have a close vigil on the performance of the PACSs as public money is involved and developmental aspiration of people through easy accessibility to credit is also involved. They should ensure that regulatory policies and provisions of appropriate Act/Rules are adhered to and complied upon within the stipulate time as scheduled. This will help the PACSs to improve the managerial effectiveness to satisfy the external controlling/supervising/regulatory authorities without which their existence will be at questioned. Thus the external authorities should keep close eyes on PACSs and as such it is observed in many cases that the external control system is quite effective in improving the managerial effectiveness and performance of PACSs compared to other parameters.
4. The PACSs should enhance the income base and try to reduce the expenses to the optimum level
5. The diversification in business portfolio should be professionally handled and carefully maintained.

Conclusion

The Management efficiency depends on how skilfully the organisation is managed for serving the cause of its members as well as for the development of the organisation. Thus, managerial effectiveness may be a corollary of management efficiency. managerial effectiveness will lead to improved performance of PACS under study. If is found from the study that the external control mechanism (mainly the government mechanism) is one of the major sources in influencing the managerial effectiveness in PACSs and there by the performance of PACSs. In this regard it can be suggested that the stakeholders of PACS such as Members, Board of Directors and employees of PACS should developed a self-sustainable business model to operationalise the PACS with independent and autonomous mechanism for its future growth..

References

- Chisasa, J. (2014). The finance-growth nexus in South Africa's agricultural sector: a structural equation modeling approach. *Banks and Bank Systems* ,9(4), 38–47.
- Das, S. (2017). Performance of the Primary Agricultural Cooperative Societies: Special Reference to Short Term Cooperative Credit Structure in North Eastern Region. *Amity Journal of Agribusiness*, 2(2), 22–29.

Dey, S., Singh, P. K., & Mhaskar, M. D. (2023). Determinants of institutional agricultural credit access and its linkage with farmer satisfaction in India: a moderated-mediation analysis. *Agricultural Finance Review*, 83(2), 211–241. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AFR-02-2022-0028>

Ndlovu, W., Mwale, M., & Zuwarimwe, J. (2022). USING A STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODEL TO EVALUATE THE ROLES OF TRADITIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN RURAL AGRICULTURE SUCCESS AND SUSTAINABILITY. *Asian Journal of Agriculture and Rural Development*, 12(4), 287–296. <https://doi.org/10.55493/5005.V12I4.4675>

Osei, C. D., & Zhuang, J. (2024). The Effects of Institutional Supports on Farm Entrepreneurial Performance: Exploring the Mediating Role of Entrepreneurial Orientation. *SAGE Open*, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440241227713>

Zhang, Y. (2023). Impact of green finance and environmental protection on green economic recovery in South Asian economies: mediating role of FinTech. *Economic Change and Restructuring*, 56, 2069–2086. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10644-023-09500-0>